

Proceedings of the
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Path to a Knowledge Society -
Managing Risks and Innovation

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Stanković, M. and Nikolić, V.

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Strategic Planning for Green and Innovative Regional Development

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Keywords

Green economy, innovation, region, strategy, assessment

Summary

Strategic regional development planning following a "green" economy and innovative development principles is complex. In this process, the content of the concept of a "green" economy, the principles, mechanisms, and tools of its implementation, as well as the innovative basis of "greening" of the economic development, ecological innovations, and institutional regulation of these processes at different levels are linked into a single system [1].

This study aims to determine the methodological foundations of developing and implementing an innovation-oriented strategy to ensure the "green" development of the regional economy.

Implementation of the systemic character of innovative processes is ensured in the regional dimension. Eco-innovations are no exception. It can be argued that multicomponent, complexity, integrity, manageability, spatial-temporal interdependence of elements (organisation in space and time), natural-resource determination (interdependence) of economic, social, and ecological development – these essential characteristics of the region determine the potential for the implementation of "green", sustainable development of the economy and, in particular, form a territorial and spatial unity for the effective systemic implementation of innovative processes [2].

The regional innovation system (RIS) is a set of economic agents and types of activities, resource provision, and institutions, as well as connections between them, necessary for increasing the efficiency of the innovation process in the region.

One of the main components of the regional innovation system is the institutional one. The role of institutions in the management system of innovative processes of the region is the main one. It consists of determining goals and priorities, programs, procedures, methods, incentives, and restrictions regarding implementing innovative activities at the level of business units and the region. From the point of view of the implementation of the "green" economy, the institutional regulation of innovation processes should be transformed both substantively and organizationally in the direction of ensuring mutual coordination of the goals of innovative development with the goals of "green" development of the regional socio-ecological and economic system.

While implementing a "green" economy, the goals of implementing innovative processes in the region also acquire "green" characteristics, and the ideal option for developing RIS is a complete and comprehensive ecologisation of innovative processes. Therefore, monitoring the peculiarities of the implementation of innovative processes in the region and assessing their development should form the basis for developing a strategy in the transition to a "green" economy.

Areas of diagnosis of the eco-innovative potential of the region (EIPR), which can form the basis of an integral assessment, are based on the evaluation of the environmental friendliness

of the following components of RIS [3]: market, scientific, production-infrastructural, institutional. The latter involves the assessment of the next: reflection of the goals of green development in the regional development strategy and program documents; share of ecologically oriented public projects and initiatives in the total number of implemented measures; share of "green" projects financed from a regional budget; actions to support eco-innovations; impact of innovative processes on the country's economy; international comparisons.

The division of regions according to the level of eco-innovation potential can be carried out based on a comparison of the integral assessment of the EIPR of a specific area with the average values within the country. This, in turn, makes it possible to group regions and recommend a particular type of strategy according to the EIPR values.

Regions with a low EIPR value can apply the strategy of adapting innovation processes to the goals of the "green" economy (orientation on anticipatory rates of economic growth due to innovations, which, however, do not belong to the group of ecological ones). Strategic goals in the field of nature management are formulated as preventing the growth of the integral eco-destructive impact of production processes on a unit of the social aggregate product.

Regions with an average EIPR value can choose a strategy of developing "green" models of production and consumption in specific, most competitive industries through the stimulation of the regional authorities' eco-innovative activities of business units. The result of implementing this strategy is to promote the broader spread of eco-

innovations in the economic sphere, ensure the region's investment attractiveness, increase its competitiveness, and strengthen the components of the EIPR.

For regions with a high EIPR, the regional development strategy can be formulated as a strategy of "green", sustainable development of the area. This strategy is characterised by the orientation of the development of all industries to the introduction of radical eco-innovations, clean and energy-saving technologies, and new business models that ensure the dematerialisation of economic growth. At the same time, efforts are expected to be focused on forming new "green" markets, industries and business models and spreading eco-innovation to all country regions through interregional interaction and cooperation.

The transformation of institutional regulation also requires a corresponding innovative change in the principles of its organisation. These changes should include decentralisation, spreading partnership models of cooperation, and promoting grassroots innovation.

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